

MS29: Validated recommendations

1. Introduction

WP7 “GDI use cases” is a key component of Pillar III in the GDI project, focusing on identifying user needs and driving the implementation of solutions through a series of use cases. By mapping *user journeys* and describing *user stories*, WP7 delivers a clear and comprehensive view of GDI’s functionalities and how users interact with them.

Deliverable 7.5¹, released in November 2024, provided recommendations for addressing the GDI use cases. Its key outcome was a cross-validation of the prototypical questions formulated by the use cases against the GDI user journeys and stories. Subsequently, the final set of user journeys and stories was finalised and documented² in January 2025 for the February (2025) Features Freeze (FFF).

This Milestone (MS29) will update the recommendations presented in D7.5 a year ago, aligning them with the finalized user journeys and stories that have been established for the February Feature Freeze (FFF).

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14537083>

² [GDI.PillarIII.UserJourneys](#)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QDeRvtW/WrhMjzBrzpetxgwezupQfo-Rx8Xd53QigTWBs/edit?tab=t.0>

2. Current status and updates

The GDI **user journeys** (see workflow depicted in Figure 1) describe the specific steps that a user will take when interacting with the GDI:

- Authenticate into GDI Federation ([ujGdio1](#))
- Data Discovery using User Portal's Data Catalogue for Authenticated Users ([ujGdio2](#))
- Data Discovery using GDI's Beacon Network for Authenticated Users ([ujGdio3](#))
- Data Access Request ([ujGdio4](#))
- Positive application response ([ujGdio5](#))
- Amend an application ([ujGdio6](#))
- Data Applications Overview (for granted access data) ([ujGdio7](#))
- Federated Data Computation ([ujGdio8](#))
 - Local computation ([ujGdio8a](#))
 - Orchestrated computation ([ujGdio8b](#))
- Download analytical (and mostly aggregated) results ([ujGdio9](#))
- Submission of an analytical workflow ([ujGdi10](#))
- Acceptance of an analytical workflow ([ujGdi11](#))
- Denial of an analytical workflow ([ujGdi12](#))

D7.5 demonstrated a core set of user journeys, from [ujGdio1](#) to [ujGdio7](#), with a stretch goal of [ujGdio8](#) and [ujGdio9](#) which detailed the executing and return of results of an analysis run on a SPE.

Since the time of publishing D7.5, user journeys [ujGdio8](#), [ujGdio9](#), [ujGdi10](#), [ujGdi11](#), and [ujGdi12](#) have been added or refined to capture all key aspects of the analytical workflow. [ujGdio8](#) is a combination of (a) local computation and (b) orchestration. In that sense, [ujGdio8\(a\)](#) makes reference to the required infrastructure on a local node so it can be connected to the GDI network, while [ujGdio8\(b\)](#) refers to the central infrastructure required to manage the network of federated nodes as well as to schedule and orchestrate a federated analysis.

User journeys 1-8a directly support the implementation of the Minimal Viable Product (MVP) together with the features by product that will be delivered by the GDI nodes. The user journeys 8b-12 enable advanced functionalities, i.e. covering federated processing towards federated learning, and are not strictly required to deliver the MVP.

Figure 1. GDI user journeys.

Subsequently, **user stories** have been derived to provide practical examples, with the set expanded inspired on the GDI use cases as recommended in D7.5:

- Enabling contact with the treating healthcare professional of patients with the same genetic and/or clinical condition as theirs to discuss possible outcomes ([usGdi01](#))
 - Refinement to a real-case scenario: Enabling contact with treating healthcare professional for a patient diagnosed with metastatic melanoma to find a second therapeutic option ([usGdi01.1](#))
- Looking up variant summary data in and across GDI datasets ([usGdi02](#))
 - Refinement to a real-case scenario: Looking up of an individual genetic variant linked to a certain disorder in a given population to explore its frequency ([usGdi02.1](#))
- Finding additional data on similar rare cancer patients to build a small cohort and understand how specific gene variants affect disease progression and/or treatment response ([usGdi03](#))
 - Parallel application to another context: Find data on individuals with TLR7 variants and diagnosed with COVID-19 to enable genetic variant risk assessment within healthcare ([usGdi03.1](#))
- Validating gene signatures for metastatic colorectal cancer as prognostic markers across multiple comparable population datasets ([usGdi04](#))
- Performing a GWAS analysis across multiple comparable population datasets to validate risk variants determining severity of COVID-19 ([usGdi05](#))

- Generalized application in the 1+MG context: Identifying genes associated with a particular disease or trait by performing GWAS analysis across federated nodes ([usGdi05.1](#))
- Finding genomic data from multiple populations to recalibrate polygenic risk scores in a specific ancestry population ([usGdi06](#))
- Finding aggregated multi-ethnic reference panels to impute missing genetic data ([usGdi07](#))

In addition, a dedicated user story (*Analysing repetitive sequences in genomic datasets across multiple national nodes using a custom workflow and tools* - [usGdi13](#)) was defined to illustrate the technical stack needed to perform a complete federated analysis³. It formed the basis of the demonstrator showcased in Deliverable 8.9⁴ and during the General Assembly in September 2025⁵. Additional efforts to envision the necessary infrastructure for federated learning are not currently being undertaken, building on the work completed so far.

³ Local Computation and Federated Computation Architecture Discussion Document - usGdi13 - CLOSED
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1FfxbH_U9bQaZFgH6u-yUYyMvqa_zKcnlx5Q6Lha1hgY/edit?tab=t.o#heading=h.cungr8gotyiv

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16882881>

⁵ D8.9 short 4 mins.mp4

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bZ3ED8NugEKOC16rmnOwJtedfYOrcemV/view?resourcekey>

3. GDI Use Cases

Cancer Research #1⁶: Melanoma use case

A clinician needs to find a second therapeutic option for his/her patient diagnosed with metastatic melanoma, justified by the identification of possible targetable mutation(s). A secondary objective is to find the molecular alterations explaining the emergence of the resistance of the primary cancer treatment.

User Story

usGdi01.1 (as a refinement of **usGdi01**): As a clinician, I want to contact the treating healthcare professional of a metastatic melanoma patient with a specific mutation so that I can explore and recommend a second therapeutic option.

Actors

Clinician/oncologist

Goals

Find a similar case in the GDI databases, by querying the network, i.e. find melanoma patients with a BRAF point mutation, treated with BRAF inhibitor Vemurafenib, who have a 12 kb deletion in the PTEN gene (known variant responsible for therapy resistance)⁷. The goal is to search for existing information on the PTEN gene, the BRAF mutation and the impact of the mutation on the Kinase pathway that can explain drug resistance in melanoma cancer patients.

Pre-conditions

The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.

User Journey

- The clinician logs into the GDI platform (**ujGdi01**) and browses available datasets (**ujGdi02** or **ujGdi03**).
- The clinician inputs a Beacon query (**ujGdi03**) using genomic coordinates or gene fusion terms, to find patients with a PTEN deletion in the genomic data. Data are filtered to focus on the most relevant cases: patients with melanoma and with details concerning the characteristics of the patient, the responses to the treatment, and survival rates.

⁶ This "Single-patient cancer use case", where a clinician looks into the GDI federated infrastructure for patients with specific characteristics similar to an in-house patient, is similar to two other cancer use cases (Chronic Myeloid Leukemia and Non Small Cell Lung Cancer) that have been defined in Deliverable 7.2 (under review)

⁷ Inspired by a scientific report: <https://doi.org/10.1200/PO.16.00054>

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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The GDI returns results, which may include a dataset relative to another patient with a similar disease and therapy history, found on one node of the network. The dataset is composed of genetic data (NGS sequencing of a melanoma treated with Vemurafenib, after developing resistance to the therapy) and the corresponding clinical data. Both raw genetic data (.Fastq file) and analysed data (.vcf file containing somatic mutations and BED file containing structural alterations) are present. Aggregated data could be visualised via a visualisation tool like in cBioportal.• If needed, a communication channel with the relevant clinical contact related to the identified patient(s) can be set up.• The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05).• The clinician downloads the genetic sequence data with the corresponding clinical data of the identified patient(s) (ujGdi09). |
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<u>Genome of Europe #1: Lookup of individual genetic variants use case</u>	
<p><i>A researcher needs to query the GDI infrastructure to know whether a specific variant linked to a certain disorder is present in a large genomic dataset collected from individuals from a particular population (e.g. region). This information could help determine if the variant is common or rare in that population, which might be important for understanding the genetic predisposition to a certain disorder.</i></p>	
<u>User Story</u>	usGdi02.1 (as a refinement of usGdi02): As a researcher, I want to query the frequency of a specific variant in a given population.
<u>Actors</u>	Researcher
<u>Goals</u>	Find human genomic datasets for a given population and explore the frequency of a specific variant.
<u>Pre-conditions</u>	The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.
<u>User Journey</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). • The researcher will construct a Beacon query (ujGdi03), i.e. the researcher inputs the details of the variant (genomic coordinates) into GDI's Beacon Network, asking whether the variant is present in specific population datasets and at what frequency. • The GDI returns aggregated results, which could include the list of human genomic datasets with individual participant data, together with a summary on group level (pre-computed and available through Beacon network), i.e. the frequency of the variant in the population or the percentage of people with this variant.

Cancer Research #2⁸: Cancer as a Rare Disease use case

A healthcare professional comes across an interesting case during one of their weekly Molecular Tumour Board (MTB) sessions at their institute. A pancreatic acinar cell carcinoma (PACC) patient is presented as having a complex histological pattern and an uncommon BRAF sequence alteration: V600_K601delinsE⁹. The clinician wonders whether the patient can be treated as if he/she has a 'classical' BRAF V600E variant and searches for any other patients harbouring the non-canonical BRAF variant identified and treated at other European centres. This information would guide the decision-making process, suggesting the most suitable therapeutic choice(s) for the patient. Since the specific BRAF variant is rarely found in this kind of cancer patients, access to a broad cohort would be helpful. The clinician would like to know if any patients corresponding to this profile exist and, if so, to learn more about their clinical history, treatment and outcome.

User Story

usGdi03: As a clinician, I want to understand from a small cohort of similar patients with a rare cancer how certain gene variants affect disease progression and/or response to treatment.

Actors

Clinician/oncologist

Goals

To search for additional data in GDI to understand whether other patients with similar clinical/molecular characteristics carrying an unusual genetic alteration in the BRAF gene have been observed and possibly treated (and how) at other European nodes. The availability of a (small) cohort of similar patients with additional information regarding the administered therapy as well as patients' responses would guide the user to choose suitable therapeutic options.

Pre-conditions

The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.

User Journey

- The clinician logs into the GDI platform ([ujGdi01](#)) and browses the available datasets ([ujGdi02](#) or [ujGdi03](#)).
- The user performs a Beacon query ([ujGdi03](#)) over the aggregate level data to get the presence of the BRAF variant (V600_K601delinsE) within the GDI infrastructure (focus on pancreatic cancer).
- The GDI user interface returns results, which includes datasets obtained from other patients with the same cancer type identified at multiple

⁸ This use case is defined in Deliverable 7.2 (under review) as the "Multi-patient cancer use case"

⁹ Inspired by a scientific report: <https://doi.org/10.1002/onco.13979>

nodes of the network. The dataset representing this small cohort is composed of genetic and corresponding clinical data. The clinical data show how the targeted BRAF sequence alterations affect prognosis or treatment outcomes.

- Assuming the presence of the variant V600_K601delinsE in only a few patients with the same cancer diagnosis, the user can extend the analysis through the Beacon both:
 - a) at gene-level, to retrieve more patients affected by the same cancer and carrying different types of BRAF variants.
 - b) at pan-cancer level, searching for any other cancer patients carrying the same genetic variant.
- The GDI user interface returns results, which could include information regarding clinical manifestations, therapy and response to treatment
- The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data ([ujGdi04](#)) and the Data Access Committee grants the access ([ujGdi05](#)).
- The clinician downloads the dataset of the small cohort of patients ([ujGdi09](#)).

Infectious Diseases #2: Genetic variant risk assessment within healthcare use case	
<p><i>A clinician assumes a potential monogenic cause for a patient with severe COVID-19 and needs to access additional data to understand whether it might be a monogenic condition. This would allow for a more precise estimate of the potential risk and potentially also guide treatment.</i></p>	
<u>User Story</u>	usGdi03.1 (as a refinement of usGdi03): As a clinician, I want to find data on COVID-19 patients with TLR7 variants to enable genetic variant-based risk assessment in healthcare.
<u>Actors</u>	Clinician
<u>Goals</u>	Find individuals with a mutation in the TLR7 gene who have been diagnosed with COVID-19
<u>Pre-conditions</u>	The clinician must be authenticated and authorised to GDI
<u>User Journey</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The clinician logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). • The clinician needs to prepare a query and filter for the Beacon Network (ujGdi03) for both human genomic data (i.e. SNPs, variants) and include phenotypic data associated with COVID-19 severity (i.e. hospitalisation, ICU admission, mortality), asking whether the variant is present in specific datasets . • The GDI Beacon Network returns results, which could include human genomic datasets annotated with Covid-19 severity indicators and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. • The clinician applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). • The clinician downloads the dataset of the small cohort with similar patients (ujGdi09).

Cancer Research #3: Metastatic Colorectal Cancer use case

A researcher aims to validate proposed gene signatures for the prognosis and survival of metastatic Colorectal Cancer (CRC) patients (ROS1, PIK3CA, LRP1B and FAT4) - that have not been fully confirmed in independent datasets. For this, the researcher aims to assemble retrospective cohorts from different data sources coming from different countries, including genomics and clinical data. The researcher has a pre-compiled pipeline relevant for the use case, to ensure that results are comparable.

User Story

usGdi04: As a researcher, I want to validate the signature of specific genes as prognostic markers for metastatic colorectal cancer across multiple comparable population datasets.

Actors

Researcher

Goals

Validate known gene signatures and discover new ones that are associated with CRC. Specifically, the aim is to identify how these gene signatures correlate with clinical factors such as tumour location, patient age and disease stage.

Pre-conditions

The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI.

User Journey

- The researcher logs into the GDI platform ([ujGdi01](#)) and browses available datasets ([ujGdi02](#) or [ujGdi03](#)).
- The researcher uses targeted search terms to filter the Central Data Catalogue ([ujGdi02](#)) such as colorectal cancer. Data are filtered to focus on the most relevant cases: CRC patients and with details concerning the patient characteristics, disease stage, diagnosis and perhaps treatment.
- The GDI returns results, which could include human genomic or genetic datasets annotated with CRC diagnosis and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network. We note that gene panels are more frequently applied in clinical settings.
- The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data ([ujGdi04](#)) and the Data Access Committee grants the access ([ujGdi05](#)).
- Once the user has the analytical workflow defined, they can submit it to acceptance into GDI ([ujGdi10](#)). GDI will check that the analytical workflow does not leak any data nor performs any undesired operation and will inform the national nodes. The analytical workflow is accepted ([ujGdi11](#)) or not accepted in GDI's system ([ujGdi12](#)) based on these conditions.

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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The researcher executes the analysis of the approved workflow by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations in several Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) (ujGdi08).• The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). |
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Infectious Diseases #1: GWAS use case

A researcher needs to query the GDI infrastructure and perform a rapid Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) in order to validate risk variants determining the severity of COVID-19. As GWAS requires large sample sizes, multiple comparable datasets are often needed.

User Story

usGdi05: As a researcher, I want to perform a GWAS across multiple comparable population datasets to validate risk variants determining severity of COVID-19.

Actors

Researcher

Goals

Find human genomic datasets that include patients with severe COVID-19. Performing a GWAS in a federated analysis scheme.

Pre-conditions

The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI

User Journey

- The researcher logs into the GDI platform ([ujGdi01](#)).
- The researcher needs to query and filter the Central Data Catalogue ([ujGdi02](#)) for both human genomic data (i.e. SNPs, variants) and phenotypic data associated with COVID-19 severity (i.e. hospitalisation, ICU admission, mortality).
- The GDI returns results, which could include human genomic datasets annotated with Covid-19 severity indicators and potentially other phenotypic information, found on one or multiple nodes of the network.
- The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data ([ujGdi04](#)) and the Data Access Committee grants the access ([ujGdi05](#)).
- Once the user has the analytical workflow defined, they can submit it to acceptance into GDI ([ujGdi10](#)). GDI will check that the analytical workflow does not leak any data nor performs any undesired operation and will inform the national nodes. The analytical workflow is accepted ([ujGdi11](#)) or not accepted in GDI's system ([ujGdi12](#)) based on these conditions.
- The researcher executes the analysis of an approved workflow by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations in several Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) ([ujGdi08](#)).
- The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing ([ujGdi09](#)).

1+MG/B1MG #1: GWAS analyses across federated nodes

A researcher wants to perform a Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) to identify genetic variants across the genome that are associated with a particular disease. The idea is to examine many common genetic variants, particularly single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), to identify statistically significant correlations with the disease of interest.

<u>User Story</u>	<u>usGdi05.1</u> (as an extension of <u>usGdi05</u>): As a researcher, I want to perform a GWAS for a particular disease or trait across multiple comparable population datasets.
<u>Actors</u>	Researcher
<u>Goals</u>	Identify genes associated with a particular disease or trait using provided whole genomes. The primary output of a GDI GWAS analysis is a list of P values, effect sizes and their directions generated from the association tests of all tested genetic variants with a phenotype of interest.
<u>Pre-conditions</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI • Relevant disease or trait and WGS data must be available for cohort building (<u>ujGdi02</u>)
<u>User Journey</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The researcher logs into the GDI platform (<u>ujGdi01</u>) • The researcher needs to define the study cohort using diseases or trait conditions (<u>ujGdi03</u>) • The GDI returns results, which include the list of human genomic datasets that have specified disease or traits. • The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (<u>ujGdi04</u>) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (<u>ujGdi05</u>). • The researcher submits the predefined GWAS pipelines to acceptance into GDI (<u>ujGdi10</u>). GDI will check that the analytical workflow does not leak any data nor performs any undesired operation and will inform the national nodes. • The analytical workflow is accepted (<u>ujGdi11</u>) or not accepted in GDI's system (<u>ujGdi12</u>) based on these conditions. • If the researcher gets the approval (<u>ujGdi05</u> and <u>ujGdi11</u>) then the researcher can access genetic sequence data indirectly. The researcher executes the GWAS analysis (approved workflow) by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations in several

	<p>Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) (ujGdio8). Individual participants' data stay within the country.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The researcher gets the relevant GWAS result data (like list of P values, Manhattan plots etc) to his research results account.• The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdio9).
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Genome of Europe #2: Recalibration of polygenic risk scores use case

A researcher wants to improve the accuracy of polygenic risk scores (PRS) for predicting disease risk in a specific ancestry population. The original PRS was developed using data from another ancestry group, but the researcher needs to adjust the PRS to be effective for individuals of the specific ancestry in their study.

User Story

usGdi06: As a researcher, I want to find genomic data from multiple populations so I can recalibrate polygenic risk scores for a specific ancestry population.

Actors

Researcher

Goals

Find human genomic data from multiple populations. This data includes both genetic information and health records, such as the presence or absence of the disease of interest. Subsequently, the PRS can be recalculated in the identified dataset.

Pre-conditions

The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI

User Journey

- The researcher logs into the GDI platform ([ujGdi01](#)).
- The researcher will construct a Beacon query ([ujGdi03](#)), i.e. the researcher inputs the details of the variants used in the original PRS into GDI's Beacon Network, asking whether the variant is present in multiple population datasets.
- The GDI returns results, which could include the list of human genomic datasets together with a summary on group level, i.e. the frequency of the variant in the population. Only datasets containing at least a predefined percentage (cutoff) of the required variants are retained.
- The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data ([ujGdi04](#)) and the Data Access Committee grants the access ([ujGdi05](#)).
- Once the user has the analytical workflow defined, they can submit it to acceptance into GDI ([ujGdi10](#)). GDI will check that the analytical workflow does not leak any data nor performs any undesired operation and will inform the national nodes. The analytical workflow is accepted ([ujGdi11](#)) or not accepted in GDI's system ([ujGdi12](#)) based on these conditions.
- The researcher executes the analysis of an approved workflow by distributing an interoperable analysis pipeline across federated locations

in several Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) ([ujGdi08](#)). Individual participants' data stay within the country.

- The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing ([ujGdi09](#)).

Genome of Europe #3: Ancestry-specific imputation use case	
<i>A researcher wants to impute a genetic dataset using ancestry-specific reference panels</i>	
<u>User Story</u>	usGdi07: As a researcher, I want to impute missing genetic information using ancestry-specific reference panels.
<u>Actors</u>	Researcher
<u>Goals</u>	Impute missing genetic data using a multi-ethnic reference panel (Genome of Europe-GoE), which can capture ancestry-specific genetic variants more effectively than general panels. This requires learning correlation patterns between SNPs in the GoE data (reference panel), then using these to infer (impute) the missing genotypes in a new sample. Typically ±1M variants are measured, and then imputed towards >40M variants using the correlation data.
<u>Pre-conditions</u>	The researcher must be authenticated and authorised to GDI
<u>User Journey</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The researcher logs into the GDI platform (ujGdi01). • The researcher needs to query and filter the Central Data Catalogue (ujGdi02) (filter on ancestry) for multi-ethnic reference panels. • The GDI returns results, which could include aggregated reference panels. • The researcher applies for data access to 1+MG data (ujGdi04) and the Data Access Committee grants the access (ujGdi05). • The researcher can download the results from his research results account for further processing (ujGdi09). The researcher accesses the reference panels (aggregated data) and executes the analysis (imputation of genetic datasets).

4. Cross-validation

Table 1. Cross-mapping of the use cases/user stories and the WP8's user journeys (1-12). The table depicts which user journeys are being used by each user case (Y).

User Story	Use cases	User Journey											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
usGdi01.1	Cancer Research #1: Melanoma	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-
usGdi02.1	Genome of Europe #1: Lookup of individual genetic variants	Y	Y	Y	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
usGdi03	Cancer Research #2: Cancer as Rare disease	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-
usGdi03.1	Infectious Diseases #2: Healthcare	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-
usGdi04	Cancer Research #3: Metastatic Colorectal Cancer	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
usGdi05	Infectious Diseases #1: GWAS	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
usGdi05.1	1+MG/B1MG #1: GWAS analyses across federated nodes	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
usGdi06	Genome of Europe #2: Recalibration of polygenic risk scores	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
usGdi07	Genome of Europe #3: Ancestry-specific imputation	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	-	-	Y	-	-	-

5. Updated recommendations

A set of user journeys have been deployed outlining a user's journey from discovering data of interest, to data access and performing an analysis, based on the requirements of the use cases. These user journeys have already helped with the deployment of the services deployed by the nodes, and the determination of which services should be deployed in production and those which could be demonstrated.

By cross-referencing the use cases, user stories, and user journeys, some remaining gaps were identified:

- Currently, there are no user stories illustrating a real-case scenario where a user wishes to amend an application ([ujGdi06](#)) or check which datasets they have access to at a given timepoint ([ujGdi07](#)).
- Currently, the user journey does not include a step for the possibility to enable secure and direct communication with the healthcare provider to exchange patient-specific information, as illustrated in [usGdi01.1](#). It involves the user going back to the relevant communication channel in the User Portal and describing and submitting their case-in-question, subsequently expecting a notification when the communication channel between them is available in a specified time frame.
- The user journey "Downloading analytical results ([ujGdi09](#))" described in the [GDI.PillarIII.UserJourneys](#) document should be extended to the situation where (aggregated) data need to be downloaded without the precondition of executing an analysis following [ujGdi08](#), as illustrated in [usGdi01.1](#), [usGdi03](#), [usGdi03.1](#), and [usGdi07](#).

